

Experimental investigation of a packed bed membrane reactor for the direct conversion of CO₂ to dimethyl ether

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the performance of a packed bed membrane reactor (PBMR) based on carbon molecular sieve membranes for the one-step CO₂ conversion to dimethyl ether (DME) is experimentally compared to that of a conventional packed bed reactor (PBR) using a CuO-ZnO-Al₂O₃/HZSM-5 bifunctional catalyst. The PBMR outperforms the PBR in most of the experimental conditions. The benefits were greater at lower GHSV (i.e., conditions that approach thermodynamic equilibrium and water formation is more severe), with both X_{CO_2} and Y_{DME} improvements of +35–40 % and +16–27 %, respectively. Larger sweep gas-to-feed (SW) ratios increase the extent of water removal (ca. 80 % at SW=5), and thus the performance of the PBMR. Nevertheless, alongside the removal of water, a considerably amount of all products are removed as well, leading to a greater improvement in the CO yield (+122 %) than the DME yield (+66 %). Higher temperatures selectively improve the rWGS reaction, leading to a lower Y_{DME} with respect to the PBR at 260 °C, due to the significant loss of methanol. Furthermore, larger transmembrane pressures (ΔP) were not beneficial for the performance of the PBMR due to the excess reactant loss (i.e., 98–99 % at $\Delta P = 3$ bar). Finally, the reactor models developed in our previous studies accurately describe the performance of both the PBR and PBMR in the range of tested conditions. This result is of high relevance, since the reactor models could be used for further optimization studies and to simulate conditions which were not explored experimentally.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, climate change is widely recognized as one of the biggest challenges of our times, with CO₂ emissions being the main responsible [1–3]. The transition towards a more sustainable and low-carbon economy is key to mitigate the effects of global warming [4]. In this scenario, the CO₂ capture and reconversion to chemicals and fuels is seen as a fundamental piece of the energy and material transition to a fossil-free economy [5–8]. There are already several CO₂ conversion technologies under investigation, with urea and methanol synthesis being the technologies with the highest readiness level [9–13]. However, among the large variety of products, dimethyl ether (DME) is particularly interesting, given its potential as clean compression ignition fuel, which could replace diesel especially in heavy transportation vehicles (i.e., trucks and ships) [14–17]. DME is commonly produced via

methanol dehydration (indirect process). However, given the higher conversion efficiency obtained when combining methanol synthesis (i.e., a thermodynamically limited reaction) and its dehydration in a single reactor (direct process), some companies, have implemented the direct – or one-step – technology at industrial scale [18].

The direct synthesis of DME is described by the following reaction scheme:

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Reaction 1–3 are typically carried out over Cu-based catalysts, with the Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃ catalyst being the most common choice in industry [19–21]. The methanol dehydration (4), requires an acid catalyst, such as γ -Al₂O₃ or zeolites (HZSM-5, FER, MOR, etc.), with the latter being currently preferred, due to the possibility to tune its acidity via the Si:Al ratio [22–24]. In the direct synthesis of DME, these two catalysts are physically mixed to form a bifunctional catalyst, although hybrid catalyst formulations have recently received considerable attention. Since the benchmark technology is based on a syngas feedstock (i.e., CO and H₂), the corresponding catalyst is not necessarily optimal when the carbon source is replaced with pure CO₂. Indeed, despite being sufficiently active, over the years, researchers have proposed a variety of different formulation [25–34].

Besides the kinetic considerations, this process is severely limited by thermodynamics, requiring low temperatures and high pressures operation to increase methanol/DME yield and syngas conversion. Such limitations become even greater when starting from pure CO₂. Indeed, all reactions (1–4) are shifted towards the right, producing large volume of water, a by-product which accumulates in the reaction environment, limiting the equilibrium and deactivating the catalyst in long-term operations [35,36].

Thus, replacing the carbon source with pure CO₂ comes with some challenges which are still under investigation. A promising strategy to overcome thermodynamic limitations is the in-situ removal of water from the reaction zone, which could be obtained via the incorporation of water-selective membranes in the catalytic bed (i.e., membrane reactor) [37–42]. In previous studies [43,44], we have proved via phenomenological reactor modeling, that when removing ca. 96 % of the water, CO₂ conversion and DME yield easily overcome thermodynamic equilibrium, with a 36 % and 46 % improvement, respectively. In the same work, we have explored the effect of the membrane properties, setting a target for the membrane selection and development.

To date, most of the work aimed at demonstrating the potential of the in-situ removal of water to enhance the DME synthesis follows a modeling approach, while only the group of Ateka and collaborators has proved the improved performance of the membrane reactor experimentally [37,45]. In these studies, the authors validated their previously developed reactor model by testing, at laboratory scale, an LTA (i.e., zeolite type A) membrane reactor using feedstocks containing CO₂/CO_x (with CO_x = CO₂ + CO) in different proportions. However, the reported DME yield for pure CO₂ feeds remains very low (~5 %), given the very high temperature (i.e., 275–325 °C) adopted in this study. Given the stronger thermodynamic limitation of the CO₂-to-DME process, lower temperature operation would be preferred to achieve higher DME yields which would, therefore, lead to the production of more water. This poses higher demands on the selection of the membrane material, especially in terms of stability. The LTA membrane proposed by Ateka et al. shows a water permeance in the order of 10⁻⁸ mol·m⁻²·s⁻¹·Pa⁻¹ and separation factors very close to (or sometimes lower than) those we measured with the carbon molecular sieve membranes (CMSM) [46] (i.e., S_{H_2O/H_2} of 1.1, $S_{H_2O/CO}$ of 2.4, S_{H_2O/CO_2} of 0.56 and $S_{H_2O/MeOH}$ of 1.8 for the LTA membrane at 275 °C). Thus, zeolite membranes display similar separation performance to CMSM, but with lower permeabilities. Besides, CMSM present improved stability with respect to zeolites in presence of water at high temperatures [36], which highlights the potential for CMSM for this application, especially when using pure CO₂ feeds that lead to larger production of water.

Carbon membranes have already been proposed in the past for their application in membrane reactors, mostly to enhance dehydrogenation reactions. Indeed, given their molecular sieving character, if the pore size of these membranes is finely tuned, H₂ (i.e., one of the smallest molecules) can be selectively separated from the reaction mixture. Itoh and Haraya developed one of the first carbon membrane reactor (CMR) to enhance the dehydrogenation of cyclohexane. Their CMR, made of a bundle of 20 carbon fibers, exceeded the equilibrium conversion at

195 °C and ambient pressure [47]. Later on, Hirota et al. improved the properties of the carbon membrane by controlling the pore size through activation with different gas/vapor atmosphere, which lead to better performance of the CMR for the dehydrogenation of methylcyclohexane in the range 200–260 °C [48]. Szejner and Sheintuch tested, for the first time, a CMR for the dehydrogenation of isobutene at very high temperature (i.e., 450–500 °C). The conversion of isobutene was significantly improved due to the H₂ removal, which was rendered even more effective thanks to the circulation of a N₂-containing sweep gas (i.e., H₂ dilution in the sweep gas as a way to increase its driving force for the permeation flux) [49]. Zhang et al. proposed a CMR to enhance the methanol steam reforming (SRM) via the in-situ removal of H₂. The authors measured a few percentage improvement in the methanol conversion and H₂ yield with respect to a conventional reactor in the range 200–250 °C, even when using N₂ as a carrier gas for the H₂ dilution [50]. Later, Sá et al. investigated, first via a numerical study, the use of either Pd or carbon membrane to enhance the SRM and to recover pure H₂ in the permeate stream. Carbon membranes were identified as a cheaper alternative to the Pd counterpart, allowing for a higher H₂ recovery, but with lower purity [51]. The same authors, few years later, experimentally investigated the use of CMR for the SRM, and found that the low H₂/H₂O perm-selectivity (i.e., 0.4 at 200 °C) caused steam depletion from the reaction zone, thus a decrease in the performance of the CMR, and higher production of CO (i.e., methanol decomposition). To solve this issue, they proposed the circulation of steam as a sweep gas to prevent its permeation from the reaction zone. In this configuration, back-permeation of water allowed to achieve higher performance with lower steam/methanol ratios in the feed [52]. This last application anticipates the challenges encountered in this study, where water must be separated and H₂ retained in the reaction zone. Finally, to underline the wide range of application of carbon membranes, Dubé et al. used a relatively large pore size carbon membrane (i.e., in the range of 0.05–1.4 μm), to obtain pure biodiesel via the transesterification of canola oil in a CMR [53,54].

Thus, the concept of using carbon membranes in membrane reactors is not new. Nevertheless, in all the applications mentioned, the CMR operates at relatively low pressure and was mostly demonstrated for H₂ separation. This underlines the challenges and novelty of this study, where keeping H₂ in the reaction zone is essential to obtain high methanol and DME selectivity, especially at high pressure and temperature (i.e., 40 bar and 200–260 °C).

In this study, a carbon membrane reactor is demonstrated for the one-step CO₂ conversion to DME. As already discussed in our previous work [43,44], the cocurrent circulation of a sweep gas containing the reactants (i.e., H₂ and CO₂) is proposed as a way to prevent reactant loss through the membrane. At the same time, this configuration allows to operate at relatively low-pressure gradient across the membrane (ΔP), since the driving force for the water separation is given by its dilution in the sweep gas. However, in our previous studies, this reactor configuration was explored via a modeling perspective. Successively, we have developed and investigated the properties of CMSM, with the objective to tune their separation performance, in view of the previously set target [46]. Based on these studies, here a CMSM is prepared and integrated in a conventional CuO-ZnO-Al₂O₃/HZSM-5 bifunctional catalyst bed. The as-obtained packed bed membrane reactor (PBMR) was tested in different conditions to investigate the effect of the main operational parameters, such as gas hourly space velocity (GHSV), temperature, sweep gas ratio (SW) and pressure gradient across the membrane (ΔP). The performance of the PBMR was compared to a PBR tested in the same conditions. Finally, the reactor model developed in our previous studies was validated with the experimental data gathered in this work. This result is of very high relevance, given that reactor model is a powerful tool for reactor design and optimization, as well as for scale-up and integration at process level.

2. Experimental

2.1. Catalyst material and characterization

The bifunctional catalyst used in this study is a physical mixture of a CuO/ZnO/Al₂O₃ (CuZA) catalyst and a HZSM-5, with a mass ratio of 1. The composition of the commercial CuO/ZnO/Al₂O₃ is reported in the [Supporting Information \(S.I.\)](#), [Table S1](#). The catalyst was provided in cylindrical pellets (5.4 × 3.6 mm) and was crushed and sieved to produce 50–125 μm particle size, to be used for the characterization techniques and reaction tests.

Typically, the γ-Al₂O₃ and the HZSM-5 are the acid catalysts used for the methanol dehydration function [55,56]. Several works have proved that the γ-Al₂O₃ suffers from strong and fast deactivation with high concentration of water in the reaction medium. Indeed, the selectivity to DME drastically decreases when the CO₂ content in the syngas feed is increased [57]. The poor activity of the CuO-ZnO-Al₂O₃/γ-Al₂O₃ bifunctional catalyst for the one-step DME synthesis from CO₂ and H₂ has also been proved in this study, using commercial γ-Al₂O₃ provided by Thermo Scientific™ (see S.I., [Fig. S1](#)). On the other hand, several studies proved that the HZSM-5 has higher activity for the DME synthesis, given the Brønsted acidity and higher stability with water [58, 59]. Zeolites are characterized by both Lewis and Brønsted acid sites and their balance is influenced by the SiO₂:Al₂O₃ (SAL) molar ratio. Better selectivity to DME have been measured with SAL between 20 and 40 [55,59]. Thus, in this work, we used HZSM-5 with a SAL of 23. The fine powder ZSM-5 zeolite was provided in ammonium form from Thermo Scientific™. The protonic form (HZSM-5) was obtained after calcination of the NH₄-ZSM-5 at 550 °C for 5 h under N₂ atmosphere [60]. The HZSM-5 powder was then pelletized, crushed, and sieved to produce 50–125 μm particle size, to be used for the characterization techniques and reaction tests.

The specific surface area (S.A.) and pore volume (P.V.) of both catalysts were determined via the BET and BJH elaboration of the N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms at −196 °C, obtained using a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 gas adsorption device. Before the measurement, the sample was degassed at 250 °C for 2 h. The catalyst density (ρ_{cat}) was measured using an automatic gas pycnometer instrument (Ultrapyc 1200e).

The CuZA catalyst reducibility was studied via temperature programmed reduction (TPR) analysis performed using a Micromeritics AutoChem 2920 equipment with a TCD detector. The analysis was carried out in the range 50–400 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C·min^{−1}, feeding 50 mL·min^{−1} of a 10 % H₂/Ar mixture. Prior to the TPR analysis, the sample was outgassed under inert conditions as for the N₂ physisorption.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis in the 2θ range 10–120° was performed on the reduced CuZA catalyst and on the HZSM-5 with a Mini-Flex600 (*Rigaku*) operating with a Ni β-filtered Cu-Kα radiant at 40 kV and 30 mA and a scan step of 0.05°/min. The diffraction peaks were identified according to the JCPDS database of reference compounds.

The acidity of the HZSM-5 was characterized via NH₃-temperature programmed desorption (TPD), carried out with the same equipment used for the TPR. Prior to the analysis, the sample was cleaned with He at 250 °C for 2 h. Thereafter, the temperature was reduced to 100 °C and the sample was saturated with a flow of 50 mL·min^{−1} of a 5 % NH₃/He mixture for 1 h. Then, the sample was purged with He until a constant baseline was measured. The TPD analysis was finally carried out increasing the temperature to 700 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C·min^{−1} under 25 mL·min^{−1} of pure He flow.

Prior to the packed bed membrane reactor experiments, the bifunctional CuO-ZnO-Al₂O₃/HZSM-5 catalyst was tested to prove its activity and stability for the CO₂ hydrogenation to DME. The catalytic tests were carried out in a stainless-steel reactor (d_{int} , 10 mm), loaded with 0.25 g of catalyst, diluted with 0.75 g of silicon carbide (SiC), to ensure isothermal operation and prevent sintering. The catalyst and the SiC

used for dilution were introduced in the reactor with the same particle size of 50–125 μm. Larger SiC particles were used as pre-heating bed, separated from the catalytic bed with c.a. 1 cm³ of quartz-wool. The reactor was placed in an electric oven and precisely heated via a heating mantle. The temperature was measured with two thermocouples, one at the beginning of the catalytic bed and the other was placed at the exit of the gases. The reaction mixture was analysed with a compact gas chromatograph (Global Analyzer Solution™, G.A.S.) equipped with a TCD detector and two packed columns (HayeSep Q 60–80 mesh and 5 Å molecular sieve) for the analysis of permanent gases (i.e., H₂, CO₂, CO and N₂) and an FID detector with capillary columns (Rtx-1, MTX-1 and MTX-QBond) for the analysis of the hydrocarbons. The experimental setup is sketched in [Fig. 1](#).

Prior to the reaction tests, the catalyst was reduced in-situ at 280 °C, with 50 mL·min^{−1} of a 50 % H₂/N₂ mixture for 4 h. The reaction tests were performed in a range of temperature and pressure of 200–260 °C and 30–40 bar, respectively. The feed contained H₂/CO₂/N₂ mixtures in different proportion to have a H₂/CO₂ molar ratio of 3 or 5, and a GHSV ranging from 1700 to 15,000 NLkg_{cat}^{−1}h^{−1}. The full carbon balance in the reaction was achieved with a maximum error of 3 %. The catalyst stability was observed with a 40 h time-on-stream test at 250 °C, 30 bar, H₂/CO₂ molar ratio of 3 and a GHSV of 11000 NLkg_{cat}^{−1}h^{−1}.

2.2. Membrane material and characterization

The carbon molecular sieve membrane (CMSM) was prepared following the procedure described in our previous study (i.e., one-dip dry carbonization step method) [46]. To ensure a good balance between water permeance and selectivity, the dipping solution was prepared with a boehmite content of 0.8 wt % and the carbonization temperature was set to 600 °C (in line with the results of our previous studies [46,61,62]). In addition, to guarantee a better adherence of the carbon layer to the ceramic support, a 1:1 dilution of the dipping solution with the NMP solvent was applied in this case. This dilution resulted in a decrease in viscosity, and thus a thinner carbon layer, as proved elsewhere [46]. Indeed, the thickness of the selective carbon layer was found to be approximately 1 μm less than the membrane tested in our previous study [62] (see SEM pictures in S.I., [Fig. S13](#)). Additionally, the lower viscosity of the dipping solution resulted in significant diffusion of the carbon into the first layer of the asymmetric ceramic support, with a thickness of approximately 34 μm (as illustrated in the SEM image in [Fig. S14](#) of the [supplementary information](#)). As a result, a higher water permeance and lower vapor/gas selectivity than those reported in our previous studies are to be expected.

Although the prepared CMSM does not correspond to the optimized membrane, this study aims at proving the concept of the packed bed membrane reactor technology and, at the same time, at validating the reactor model previously developed [43,44].

The membrane was cut and sealed using two metallic tubes: 1) a dead-end tube and 2) a tube welded to a Swagelok connection. The tubes were connected to the membrane with a hydraulic crimping machine (FINN-POWER), applying a pressure of 20 psi and using graphite tape for the deformation as well as to protect the membrane. After sealing, a CMSM with total active length of 3.7 cm was obtained, as shown in [Fig. 2](#).

Prior to the reaction tests, the membrane permeation properties were tested. The permeation tests were carried out with the same procedure and experimental setup described in our previous study [46]. Vapor/gas separation performance were derived via binary mixture tests, exposing the membrane to an equimolar mixture of H₂O and one of each gas (i.e., H₂, CO₂, CO and DME). The permeance of methanol was derived via pure vapor permeation tests. The tests were carried out with a total pressure gradient (ΔP) across the membrane of 3 bar and in the temperature range of 200–260 °C, which is relevant for the reaction.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the experimental setup used for the catalytic tests. Gases (H₂, CO₂ and N₂) are fed from bottles (Linde). FC indicates mass flow controllers, TI and TC represent thermocouples and controllers, respectively. Pressure is controlled via a back pressure control system (BPC).

Fig. 2. Carbon molecular sieve membrane sealed with a dead-end metallic tube from one side, and a metallic tube with a Swagelok connection on the other side.

2.3. Packed bed membrane reactor setup and testing

A schematic representation of the setup used for the packed bed membrane reactor (PBMR) tests is given in Fig. 3. The membrane reactor is a stainless-steel vessel (OD 28.5 mm, L 150 mm) with a top flange for the connection of the membrane tube. Both a sweep gas and a permeate line are connected to the inner side of the membrane via the top flange. The catalyst bed is placed in the outer space. Gases (H₂, CO₂ and N₂) are fed via mass flow controller (FC) from Bronkhorst, from gas cylinders (Linde). N₂ is only fed during the reduction protocol (FC105) and during reaction tests as external standard (FC106), to dilute both the retentate and permeate stream, via a three-way valve (3WV). H₂ and CO₂ are fed both in the reaction zone (FC103 and FC104), and in the sweep gas (FC101 and FC102), to limit the permeation of reactants. The pressure in the reaction and permeation zone is regulated via two back pressure controllers BPC106 and BPC107, respectively, and measured via pressure indicators PI110 and PI220, upstream the reactor. The membrane reactor is heated via an external jacket through the temperature control system TC202-TI202. The reactor is then placed in an electric oven to also preheat the feed lines. Temperature is measured inside the membrane tube (TI205), at the entrance of the catalytic bed (TI207) and at the exit of the catalytic bed (TI206), in order to monitor whether the

operation is isothermal. The retentate and the permeate lines can be sent to the analysis section via a six-way valve (6WV), after dilution with the N₂ stream, as described above. Both the retentate and permeate mixture were analyzed with the same compact gas chromatograph described in Section 2.1.

Once connected the membrane to the top flange, the reactor was closed and packed via a funnel, as follows (from bottom to top):

1. A layer of quartz wool (ca. 5 mL).
2. 25 g (ca. 15 mL) of SiC (100–150 μm), to fill the volume corresponding to the bottom metallic connection of the membrane.
3. 20 mL of catalyst bed, composed of: 1.5 g of CuO/ZnO/Al₂O₃, 1.5 g of HZSM-5 and 25 g of SiC, with an average particle size of 100–150 μm.
4. 25 g (ca. 15 mL) of larger (250 μm) SiC, to fill the volume corresponding to the top metallic connection of the membrane and to function as a preheating bed. Given the high thermal conductivity of SiC.

In this configuration, the catalyst is only in contact with the membrane active layer, while inert material (SiC) is used to dilute the catalyst to prevent hot spots formation and, at the same time, to ensure the desired aspect ratio of the catalyst bed.

To properly compare the two reactor technologies under the same conditions, the packed bed reactor (PBR) experiments were repeated using the configuration shown in Fig. 3 and packing procedure described above, but replacing the membrane with a stainless steel tube with the same size of the CMSM.

Prior to the reaction tests, the catalyst was reduced in-situ at 280 °C with a mixture of 100 mL/min 50 vol % H₂ in N₂ for 24 h. In the PBMR configuration, 100 mL/min of H₂ was also fed in the sweep gas, to prevent H₂ permeation. Thereafter the reaction tests were carried out in the temperature range 200–260 °C, a pressure of 40 bar in the reaction

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of the experimental setup used for the PBMR tests. Gases (H₂, CO₂ and N₂) are fed from bottles (Linde). FC indicates mass flow controllers, TI and TC represent thermocouples and controllers, respectively. Pressure is controlled via a back pressure control system (BPC). 3WV and 6WV corresponds to the 3-way and 6-way valves respectively.

zone (P^R), H₂/CO₂ molar ratio of 3 both in the feed to the reaction zone and in the sweep gas, a GHSV in the range 400–2600 NLkg⁻¹h⁻¹. The ΔP was varied from 0 to 3 bar and a sweep gas ratio (SW) ranging from 1 to 5 was used. An overview of the experiments carried out is given in Table 1. Prior to each experiment, the PBMR_1 test was repeated to confirm that both the membrane and the catalyst were stable. A stability test was finally performed in the conditions of PBMR_5 for 120 h.

The reaction performance in terms of CO₂ conversion (X_{CO_2}), product yield (Y_i) and selectivity (S_i) were determined using the methodology already reported in our previous work [43] (Eq. 1–6). The product removal (R_i) was also quantified for each PBMR experiment, according to Eq. 7. Finally, the loss (L_i) or cofeeding (CoF_i) of reactants (i.e., CO₂

and H₂), was calculated via Eqs. 8 and 9, respectively, where the transmembrane flow ($F_{i,imb}$) for the reactants is calculated as for the CO₂ (Eq. 4). Finally, the improvement achieved by the PBMR in relation to the PBR in terms of reactor performance is calculated according to Eq. 10., where X_{PBMR} and X_{PBR} indicate either CO₂ conversion or product yield evaluated for the PBMR and the PBR, respectively.

$$X_{CO_2} = \frac{F_{CO_2,0}^R - F_{CO_2}^R + F_{CO_2,imb}^R}{F_{CO_2,0}^R + F_{CO_2,imb}^R} \quad (1)$$

$$Y_i = \frac{N_{c,i}(F_i^R + F_i^P)}{F_{CO_2,0}^R + F_{CO_2,imb}^R} \quad (2)$$

Table 1

Overview of the PBMR and PBR experiments carried out with the corresponding operating conditions.

ID (–)	GHSV (NL kg ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)	T (°C)	P^R (bar)	ΔP (bar)	SW (–)	(H ₂ /CO ₂) [*] (–)
PBMR_1	400	200	40	0	1	3
PBMR_2	1300	200	40	0	1	3
PBMR_3	2600	200	40	0	1	3
PBMR_4	400	200	40	0	3	3
PBMR_5	400	200	40	0	5	3
PBMR_6	400	220	40	0	5	3
PBMR_7	400	240	40	0	5	3
PBMR_8	400	260	40	0	5	3
PBMR_9	2600	200	40	1.5	1	3
PBMR_10	2600	200	40	3	1	3
PBR_1	400	200	40	–	–	3
PBR_2	1300	200	40	–	–	3
PBR_3	2600	200	40	–	–	3
PBR_4	400	220	40	–	–	3
PBR_5	400	240	40	–	–	3
PBR_6	400	260	40	–	–	3

*In the PBMR tests, the same H₂/CO₂ was used for both the reaction zone feed and the sweep gas

$$S_i = \frac{Y_i}{X_{CO_2}} \quad (3)$$

$$F_{CO_2,mb} = F_{CO_2,0}^P - F_{CO_2}^P \text{ transmembrane flow} \quad (4)$$

$$F_{CO_2,mb}^* = 0 \text{ if } F_{CO_2,mb} \leq 0 \text{ Reactant loss} \quad (5)$$

$$F_{CO_2,mb}^* = F_{CO_2,mb} \text{ if } F_{CO_2,mb} > 0 \text{ Reactant cofeeding} \quad (6)$$

$$R_i = \frac{F_i^P}{F_i^P + F_i^R} \quad (7)$$

$$L_i = \frac{-F_{i,mb}}{F_{i,0}^R} \text{ if } F_{CO_2,mb} \leq 0 \text{ Reactant loss} \quad (8)$$

$$CoF_i = \frac{F_{i,mb}}{F_{i,0}^R} \text{ if } F_{CO_2,mb} > 0 \text{ Reactant cofeeding} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Improvement}(\%) = \frac{X_{PBMR} - X_{PBR}}{X_{PBR}} \bullet 100 \quad (10)$$

3. Modeling

The 1D-pseudo homogeneous PBR and PBMR reactor model described in our previous study [44] were used to simulate the experiments carried out in this work. Being the catalyst particle size in the order of 50–125 μm , internal mass transfer limitations were neglected. Furthermore, in all experimental conditions, temperature gradients along the catalyst bed, as well as between reaction and permeation zone, were found negligible. Thus, the model was considered isothermal. The model equations and boundary conditions are summarized in Table 2, where the superscripts R and P refer to the reaction and permeation zone, respectively.

Mass balances were solved in terms of bulk concentration of each component ($C_{i,b}^R$ or $C_{i,b}^P$) as a function of the reactor length (z). The mass balance in the reaction zone (Eq. 11) is based on a reaction term (R_i) and a permeation flux ($J_{perm,i}$) of the species through the membrane. The mass balance of the permeation zone, reported in Eq. 12, accounts only for the permeation flux (i.e., no reaction), where a_{memb} is the membrane area per reactor volume.

The reaction term (R_i , Eq. 15) accounts for the reaction rates for both the Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃ catalyst ($r'_{i,cat1}$) and the HZSM-5 catalyst ($r'_{i,cat2}$), which follow the kinetic model of Portha et al. [63] and Ortega et al. [64], respectively (details on the kinetic model and its validation with our experimental data are given in S.I., Section 4). Besides the reaction rates defined based on the volume of the catalysts (r'_i), R_i is a function of

Table 2

Mass and momentum balance equations and corresponding boundary conditions for the 1D packed bed reactor and packed bed membrane reactor models, in the hypothesis of plug flow. These equations apply for both the heterogeneous and the pseudo-homogeneous reactor models.

Equation	B.C. z = 0	B.C. z = L
Mass balance – Reaction zone		
$\frac{\partial (v^R C_{i,b}^R)}{\partial z} = R_i - a_{memb} \bullet J_{perm,i}$ (11)	$C_{i,b}^R = C_{i,b}^{R,IN}$	$\frac{\partial C_{i,b}^R}{\partial z} = 0$
Mass balance – Permeation zone		
$\frac{\partial (v^P C_i^P)}{\partial z} = a_{memb} \bullet J_{perm,i}$ (12)	$C_{i,b}^P = C_{i,b}^{P,IN}$	$\frac{\partial C_{i,b}^P}{\partial z} = 0$
Continuity equation – Reaction zone		
$-\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\rho_f \frac{1}{\beta} \frac{\partial P^R}{\partial z} \right) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} (M_i R_i - a_{memb} \bullet J_{perm,i})$ (13)	$\frac{\partial P^R}{\partial z} = \beta_0 v_{in}^R$	$P^R = P^R_{out}$
Continuity equation – Permeation zone		
$-\frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho_f v^P) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} (a_{memb} \bullet J_{perm,i})$ (14)	$v^P = v_{in}^P$	$\frac{\partial v^P}{\partial z} = 0$

the volumetric dilution of the catalyst bed (D_{cat}), the bed porosity (ϵ_{bed}), the volume fraction (x_{cat}) and apparent density (ρ_{cat}) of each catalyst (i.e., Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃ and HZSM-5).

$$R_i = D_{cat} (1 - \epsilon_{bed}) \left(x_{cat1} \rho_{cat1} r'_{i,cat1} + x_{cat2} \rho_{cat2} r'_{i,cat2} \right) \quad (15)$$

The permeation flux ($J_{perm,i}$) of the species through the membrane is described by the following equation:

$$J_{perm,i} = \phi_i (P_i^R - P_i^P) \quad (16)$$

Where P_i^R and P_i^P are the partial pressure of component i in the reaction and permeation zone, respectively. The permeance of each species (ϕ_i) as a function of temperature was derived experimentally for the CMSM and was fitted with an Arrhenius law (see S.I., Fig. S7), in order to implement the membrane properties in the reactor model. More details on the membrane properties are discussed in Section 4.2.

Eq. 13 represents the continuity equation of the reaction zone which is used to determine the pressure drop ($\partial P^R / \partial z$) along the reactor. The friction factor (β) is calculated via the Ergun equation (Eq. 17), where μ_f is the fluid viscosity, ρ_f is the fluid density, calculated via the Peng-Robinson equation of state and D_p is the particle diameter. The velocity of the gas mixture in the reaction zone (v^R) varies along the reactor axis (z) according to the Darcy equation (Eq. 17).

$$\beta = 150 \frac{(1 - \epsilon_{bed})^2 \mu_f}{\epsilon_{bed}^3 D_p^2} + 1.75 \frac{\rho_f (1 - \epsilon_{bed}) |v|}{\epsilon_{bed}^2 D_p} \quad (17)$$

$$v^R = -\frac{1}{\beta} \frac{\partial P^R}{\partial z} \quad (18)$$

The continuity equation for the permeation zone (Eq. 13) is used to determine the velocity profile v^P . The total pressure (P^P) in the permeation zone is assumed constant. Indeed, due to the absence of solid particles, the pressure drop of the gas flowing in the membrane tube is negligible.

To model the PBR, the same set of equations was solved, considering that the membrane area per reactor volume (a_{memb}) is zero and there is no distinction between permeation and reaction zones.

In conclusion, a comparison was made between the results obtained from the use of both the PBR and PBMR and the thermodynamic limitation. The equilibrium conversion and product yield were determined through two distinct approaches: 1) utilizing Aspen Plus (RGibbs reactor), and 2) utilizing the reactor model while ensuring that the reactor length was sufficient to achieve the thermodynamic limit, in the absence of the membranes. Both methodologies produced identical results.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Catalyst activity tests

The physical properties of the CuO/ZnO/Al₂O₃ (CuZA) and HZSM-5 catalyst are reported and shortly discussed in S.I. (Section 1). Fig. 4a depicts the DME (Y_{DME}), methanol (Y_{MeOH}) and CO yield (Y_{CO}) as a function of temperature at 40 bar, measured with a GHSV of 3400 $\text{NLkg}_{cat}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ and a feed composition of CO₂/H₂/N₂ = 3/9/1. The yield of all products expectedly increases with temperature, since the operation is kinetically limited (i.e., thermodynamic equilibrium is not yet achieved) at the tested GHSV. The Y_{DME} and Y_{CO} show a crossover behaviour at 220 °C. For a $T \leq 220$ °C, $Y_{DME} > Y_{CO}$ (i.e., DME selectivity larger than 70 %); for a $T \geq 220$ °C, the situation is reversed. The same trend repeats at all pressures and H₂:CO₂ ratios (see S.I., Fig. S5 and S6). However, both pressure and H₂ concentration affect positively the CO₂ conversion (X_{CO_2}) and the DME selectivity, leading to a shift in the Y_{DME} - Y_{CO} crossover point towards higher temperatures. Additionally,

Fig. 4. DME, Methanol and CO yield as a function of temperature (a) and as a function of the time on stream at 250 °C (b) measured at $3400 \text{ NLkg}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$ and a feed composition of $\text{CO}_2/\text{H}_2/\text{N}_2 = 3/9/1$.

from Fig. S5c and d, it can be observed that as pressure is raised from 30 to 40 bar, the DME and CO selectivity experience a relatively smaller increase and decrease, respectively. Nevertheless, the selectivity of methanol appears to be barely affected (i.e., changes fall within the range of experimental error) or somewhat decreases. This implies that, under these circumstances, either the rWGS or methanol/DME decomposition to CO and H₂ over the acid sites of the HSZM-5 is favored [65]. Given the absence of any other detected carbon species, we can exclude the possibility of methanol/DME further conversion to olefins on the HSZM-5.

Besides DME, methanol and CO, no other products were detected, and full carbon balance was closed with a maximum error of 3 %. Thus, the experiments do not reveal any evidence of side reactions (e.g., methanol to gasoline).

In addition, the product yield measured at 250 °C (Fig. 4b) did not show any significant changes within 40 h of time on stream, indicating that, in these conditions and timespan, catalyst deactivation appears to be negligible.

Finally, the experimental data obtained in this study were used to validate the kinetic model described in our previous publication [44] (see S.I., Section 4). The alignment between kinetic predictions and experimental data further supports the absence of deactivation or any other phenomena that would otherwise alter kinetic activity of the catalyst upon operation.

4.2. Separation performance of the CMSM

The membrane properties in terms of water permeance ($\varphi_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$) and

Table 3

Properties of the membrane of this work compared to the average properties of the CMSM studied in previous publications and to the target set via the optimization proposed by us in a previous work. All membrane properties are reported at 200 °C.

Membrane property	Target [43]	CMSM Previous works [46,62]	CMSM This work
$\varphi_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ ($\text{mol}\cdot\text{Pa}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)	$4\cdot 10^{-7}$	$(1.25\text{--}7.54)\cdot 10^{-7}$	$1.39\cdot 10^{-6}$
$S_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{H}_2}$ (-)	50	1.68–6.74	2.06
$S_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}_2}$ (-)	30	5.33–14.6	2.37
$S_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}}$ (-)	30	8.90–49	3.99
$S_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{MeOH}}$ (-)	10	4.01–17	2.39
$S_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{DME}}$ (-)	–	–	2.61

perm-selectivity ($S_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/i}$) derived at 200 °C are reported in Table 3. For comparison, the average properties of the membranes reported in our previous works, as well as the target properties set via the optimization study are also reported. It is clear that the target $\varphi_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ was successfully achieved in the membranes we previously developed, while the targets in $S_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/i}$ were in most cases not achieved. With respect to the new membrane prepared in this work, it evidently has a much greater permeance (i.e., $\varphi_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ in the order of $10^{-6} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{Pa}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$), and a consequently lower selectivity (i.e., $S_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/i}$, especially for the H₂O/CO₂, H₂O/CO and H₂O/MeOH pairs) than the previous membranes. This is in line with the decrease in carbon layer thickness of this new membrane with respect to the previous, as discussed in Section 2.2. Nevertheless, an improvement of the separation properties (i.e., increase in selectivity) could be obtained by depositing one or more carbon layers on top of the first one, using the same synthesis method described in previous studies [46,61].

In general, the highest $\varphi_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ corresponds to the lowest $S_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/i}$ in the range reported in Table 3. For all membranes, $S_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{H}_2}$ is always the smallest perm-selectivity, due to the very similar size of the two molecules. Indeed, despite capillary condensation phenomena, H₂O and H₂ are believed to compete for their access to the molecular sieving pores, as discussed in previous studies [46,61]. Furthermore, $S_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}}$ is always greater than $S_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}_2}$, since CO₂ shows significant affinity to the membrane surface, favoring adsorption diffusion over molecular sieving for some membranes. On the other hand, $S_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}}$ and $S_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{MeOH}}$ show the expected behavior, based on the predictions of the modeling study previously reported [43], and the corresponding values achieve the target in most of the cases.

Given the challenges in working with DME in a laboratory setting (due to its vapor/gas equilibrium at room conditions), the permeance of DME through CMSM could not be measured in our previous studies. Nevertheless, this parameter was believed to be less relevant for the optimization/selection of the CMSM. For the first time, the permeance of DME through CMSM is measured in this work. Interestingly, φ_{DME} was found to decrease strongly with temperature (see S.I., Fig. S7a), indicating that adsorption diffusion is the dominant transport mechanism for DME. Its activation energy is quite large when compared to CO₂ (i.e., -163 vs $-4.09 \text{ kJ}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$) and the $S_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{DME}}$ spikes from 2.61 to 237 when temperature increases from 200° to 260°C. This means that DME adsorbs more strongly on the CMSM surface, such that its transport due to surface diffusion is more limited at higher temperatures.

More details on the permeation properties of this membrane as a

function of temperature are reported in S.I., together with the parameters derived fitting φ_1 with the Arrhenius law.

4.3. Packed bed membrane reactor performance and model validation

4.3.1. Effect of the GHSV

Fig. 5 shows that the reactor model describes quite accurately the performance of both the PBR and PBMR as a function of the GHSV in terms of CO₂ conversion (Fig. 5a) and product yield (Fig. 5b). The product selectivity is also reported for completion in S.I. (see Fig. S8). The PBMR outperforms the PBR in the entire range of GHSV explored, with greater improvement as the GHSV decreases (i.e., closer to thermodynamic equilibrium), as reported in Table 4. At lower GHSV, the concentration of water in the reaction zone is higher, which makes its removal via the CMSM more effective.

Nevertheless, the improvement in the Y_{DME} is considerably lower than the increase in the Y_{CO} . This is partly explained by a relatively low concentration of methanol in the reaction zone, which limits the extent of DME synthesis. Indeed, despite CO and DME removal being quite similar (i.e., 45 % and 47 % at GHSV of 400 $NLkg_{cat}^{-1}h^{-1}$, respectively), methanol is being removed as much as water (i.e., 52 % and 49 % at GHSV of 400 $NLkg_{cat}^{-1}h^{-1}$, respectively). This behavior is also discussed in our previous work [44], where it is observed that even for large $S_{H_2O/MeOH}$ (ca. 5), the methanol loss through the membrane notably decreases the Y_{DME} in the PBMR.

Severe removal of CO, as measured within the PBMR experiments, is detrimental for this process because, together with water removal, it enhances the rWGS reaction considerably, leading to unselective CO₂ and H₂ consumption. At the same time, the permeated CO cannot be further converted to methanol (i.e., via the CO hydrogenation). This explains the higher selectivity to CO obtained in the PBMR with low $S_{H_2O/CO}$ (i.e., 26.3 % vs 35 % obtained at a GHSV of 400 $NLkg_{cat}^{-1}h^{-1}$ with the PBR and PBMR, respectively).

An effective solution to prevent methanol permeation is the recirculation of permeated methanol in the sweep gas together with H₂ and CO₂, as a way to reduce the driving force across the membrane. However, this solution could not be tested experimentally due to the setup limitations (i.e., the setup does not have a recirculation loop, and no feeding system for methanol).

In principle, this solution could be adopted also to prevent CO permeation. Nevertheless, according to the PBMR modeling predictions with the membrane properties measured experimentally in previous

Table 4

Improvement of the reaction performance (CO₂ conversion, DME yield and CO yield) of the PBMR with respect to the PBR evaluated experimentally.

Reaction performance	Improvement determined at GHSV of:		
	400 $NLkg_{cat}^{-1}h^{-1}$	1300 $NLkg_{cat}^{-1}h^{-1}$	2600 $NLkg_{cat}^{-1}h^{-1}$
CO ₂ conversion	+40.5 %	+37.3 %	+34.9 %
DME yield	+26.8 %	+21.8 %	+15.8 %
CO yield	+75.3 %	+43.1 %	+21.8 %

works (i.e., which met the target previously set for $S_{H_2O/CO}$), the removal of CO is not relevant. Thus, in such condition, the improvement in DME yield becomes similar to those in CO₂ conversion, meaning that the product distribution is not much affected with respect to the PBR.

4.3.2. Effect of the SW ratio

As thoroughly studied in our previous study using modeling tools [43], Fig. 6a demonstrates experimentally that large SW ratios indeed increase the reaction performance (i.e., CO₂ conversion and product yield). The effect of SW on the product selectivity is also reported for completion in S.I. (see Fig. S9). Greater SW ratios remarkably increase the extent of product removal (Fig. 6b). Indeed, the water removal (R_{H_2O}) increases from 52 % to 80 % along with the removal of all the other products, from 45 % to 47 % to 65–68 %, upon increasing SW from 1 to 5, respectively, with the R_{DME} being the lowest. As already discussed, this leads to a larger improvement in the CO rather than the DME formation with respect to the PBR (i.e., 66 % and 112 % improvement for Y_{DME} and Y_{CO} , respectively, at SW of 5).

Furthermore, as also observed via the model prediction [43], a low S_{H_2O/H_2} and/or S_{H_2O/CO_2} , in this particular reactor configuration (i.e., circulation of a sweep gas containing the reactants), leads to the back-permeation of reactants from the permeation to the reaction zone. Indeed, larger SW ratios leads to a more efficient removal of the water, which, as a consequence, increases CO₂ and H₂ conversion. As a result, the CO₂ and H₂ concentration in the reaction zone decreases axially, while their concentration in the permeation zone is barely affected due to the high dilution of the permeating species in the sweep gas. Thus, given their transmembrane concentration gradient, the CO₂ and H₂ permeate towards the reaction zone (i.e., CO₂ and H₂ cofeeding).

However, Fig. 6b shows that the extent of CO₂ and H₂ cofeeding (CoF_{CO_2} and CoF_{H_2}) is not significantly affected by the SW ratio in this range (i.e., SW of 1–5). This could be attributed to the significantly high φ_{CO_2} and φ_{H_2} for this CMSM, which leads to a significant CoF_{CO_2} and

Fig. 5. CO₂ conversion (a) and DME and CO yield (b) as a function of the GHSV for both the PBR and PBMR derived experimentally (markers) and via simulations (continuous lines). Other operating conditions: $P^R = 40$ bar, $T = 200$ °C and a feed composition of H₂/CO₂ = 3; a $SW = 1$ and $\Delta P = 0$ bar were used for the PBMR.

Fig. 6. CO₂ conversion and product yield (a) and product removal/reactant cofeeding (b) for the PBMR at different SW ratios (1, 3, and 5) derived experimentally and via simulations, in comparison with the reaction performance of the PBR obtained in the same conditions. Other operating conditions: $P^R = 40$ bar, $T = 200$ °C, a GHSV of $400 \text{ NLkg}_{cat}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$ and a feed composition of $H_2/CO_2 = 3$; $\Delta P = 0$ bar were used for the PBMR.

CoF_{H_2} of ca. 28 % and 19 %, respectively, already at SW of 1.

Finally, Fig. 6a shows that the PBMR model describes very well the reaction performance, including the effect of SW ratio. Nevertheless, the model slightly underpredicts the Y_{CO} and Y_{MeOH} , while it estimates a slightly higher Y_{DME} . This discrepancy is explained by the fact that the membrane properties have been measured with binary mixture (i.e., vapor/gas), rather than with a multicomponent system. Thus, interactions among the species are neglected also in the model. However, given its large kinetic diameter, DME is expected to permeate less when competing with the other species in the system, which could explain the lower Y_{DME} measured experimentally.

4.3.3. Effect of temperature

The effect of temperature on the reaction performance is depicted in Fig. 7 (see Fig. S10 in S.I. for product selectivity), where the thermodynamic limit is also reported for comparison. In these experiments, a SW of 5 was used given the results reported in the previous paragraph. The PBMR and PBR models accurately describe also the effect of temperature on the CO₂ conversion and product yield, predicting a slightly higher Y_{DME} and lower Y_{CO} and Y_{MeOH} for the PBMR, with respect to their experimental values, as previously discussed.

Given the low GHSV used in these experiments, the system is more affected by the thermodynamic equilibrium, especially at high temperature, which corresponds to faster reaction rates. Indeed, CO₂ conversion and product yield of the PBR achieve their thermodynamic limit at 260 °C (i.e., continuous line in Fig. 7). It should be noted that the Y_{CO} of the PBR is slightly larger than its thermodynamic value for temperatures below 260 °C. Since CO is not only a product in this reaction network, but also a reactant for the methanol synthesis (i.e., reversible reactions in series), a Y_{CO} beyond the thermodynamic curve indicates that the extent of CO conversion to methanol is not at its maximum value (i.e., CO hydrogenation has not achieved equilibrium). More details on this observation are given in S.I. (Section 3). As a matter of fact, the profile of Y_{CO} in a conventional PBR is characterized by a maximum, after which CO starts to react to form methanol and finally achieves thermodynamic equilibrium.

The behavior of the PBMR with temperature is more complex than that in PBR, due to the alteration of the thermodynamic equilibrium caused by the product/reactant separation. Nevertheless, since the membrane removes products more effectively when their concentration in the reaction zone is higher (i.e., closer to the thermodynamic

equilibrium), the PBMR trend with temperature resembles that of the PBR.

From Fig. 7a, it is clear that the introduction of the membrane enhances the CO₂ conversion in the entire temperature region explored (i.e., 200–260 °C), exceeding thermodynamic equilibrium for temperatures greater than 220 °C. As a matter of fact, water is the main reaction by-product of both the rWGS and CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol and DME, which means that the in-situ removal of water, and any other products, positively affects CO₂ conversion.

However, a higher X_{CO_2} does not necessarily mean a higher selectivity to the desired product. Indeed, Fig. 7b clearly shows that the improvement in Y_{DME} becomes negligible for temperature higher than 200 °C. Furthermore, it should be noted that although the PBMR yields an increase of approximately 67 % in Y_{DME} at 200 °C, the PBR exhibits a 9.5 % higher Y_{DME} than the PBR when operating at 260 °C. This indicates that at the highest tested temperature, the PBMR leads to a lower Y_{DME} than the PBR. This behavior is explained by the extremely high extent of product removal obtained in these conditions. Indeed, for temperatures above 200 °C, R_i achieves ca. 98–99 % for all products, indicating that all methanol is being removed from the reaction zone and cannot be effectively converted to DME. As a consequence, Y_{DME} never exceeds its thermodynamic limit in these conditions.

At the same time, as temperature increases, the PBMR considerably improves the performance of the rWGS reaction well above its thermodynamic equilibrium, leading to a Y_{CO} ca. 2.7 times higher than the PBR at 260 °C (Fig. 7c). Indeed, CO formation is favored by high temperature, given the endothermicity of the reaction. In addition, due to the reaction stoichiometry, the rWGS requires a lower H₂:CO₂ ratio than the methanol synthesis, which makes it even faster and favored in these conditions, where H₂ is being removed more than CO₂ (see φ_i trend vs temperature in S.I., Fig. S7). All this explains why, given the similar extent of methanol and CO removal, the CO formation is favored over methanol synthesis (Fig. 7c and d).

It should be noted that thermodynamic limitations are altered by the presence of the membrane. However, qualitative thermodynamic considerations are still valid, since the presence of the membrane alters the composition of the system, which corresponds to a different chemical equilibrium (i.e., dynamic equilibrium) [66].

As already anticipated, the product removal increases to ca. 98–99 % for all products as temperature increases above 200 °C, despite both φ_{H_2O} and φ_{MeOH} decrease with temperature, due to their permeation

Fig. 7. CO₂ conversion (a), DME yield (b), CO yield (c) and methanol yield (d) as a function of temperature for the PBMR and PBR derived experimentally and via simulations. Other operating conditions: $P^R=40$ bar, a GHSV of $400 \text{ NLkg}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$ and a feed composition of $\text{H}_2/\text{CO}_2 = 3$; $SW=5$ and $\Delta P=0$ bar were used for the PBMR.

mechanism. However, as shown in our previous work [43], once the target permeance has been achieved, its effect on the reaction performance, including product removal, is not relevant. Given the very high permeance of the CMSM used in this work, also at the highest temperature (i.e., 260 °C), $\varphi_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is 2.6 times higher than its target value. In addition, given the fast reaction rates at higher temperatures, a large gradient in the driving force across the membrane develops for all products, favoring their removal from the reaction zone.

Alongside the increase in the product removal, at higher temperature also the reactant cofeeding becomes consistently higher, with CoF_{CO_2} and CoF_{H_2} achieving ca. 130 %. Note that values higher than 100 % are possible due to the circulation of the sweep gas (i.e., for $SW=1$, the maximum cofeeding is 100 %, which corresponds to the situation in which all the CO₂ and/or H₂ back-permeate to the reaction zone). Reactant cofeeding is also not highly beneficial to the PBMR performance. When either CO₂ or H₂ are introduced in the reaction zone at a specific length of the catalytic bed, their residence time is lower than if they were introduced at the reactor inlet. Therefore, they do not have enough contact time with the catalyst, which overall leads to a lower conversion/yield (see Eqs. 1–4).

4.3.4. Effect of pressure gradient (ΔP)

Experiments with a ΔP larger than 0 were particularly difficult to conduct, given the very high permeability of the CMSM used in this work. Indeed, as soon as a slightly positive ΔP is imposed, even with no reaction, all the gas permeates from the reaction to the permeation zone, leading to a drop in the retentate pressure (P^R), until it equilibrates with the permeate pressure (P^P). To prevent this situation, a high flow rate had to be used as feed to the reaction zone (i.e., GHSV of $2600 \text{ NLkg}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$), to ensure that enough gas was left in the reaction zone to keep the pressure.

Given this initial consideration, the extent of product removal and reactant loss expectedly achieves ca. 98–99 % for a $\Delta P=3$ bar (Fig. 8b), which leads to very poor performance of the PBMR (i.e., CO₂ conversion 16 % lower than the PBR). This was also confirmed by the simulations, where already at a length of 1.86 cm (i.e., in the middle of the PBMR), the CO₂ and H₂ flow in the reaction zone becomes zero. A similar situation applies at $\Delta P=1.5$ bar, where CO₂ and H₂ flow becomes zero at the outlet of the reaction zone (see flow profiles in S.I., Fig. S12).

Thus, for a $\Delta P > 0$, the PBR outperform the PBMR both in terms of CO₂ conversion and product yield (Fig. 8a) and selectivity (Fig. S11 in S.

Fig. 8. CO₂ conversion and product yield (a) and product removal/reactant cofeeding (b) for the PBMR at different ΔP (0, 1.5, and 3) derived experimentally and via simulations, in comparison with the reaction performance of the PBR obtained in the same conditions. Other operating conditions: $P^R = 40$ bar, $T = 200$ °C, a GHSV of $2600 \text{ NLkg}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$ and a feed composition of $\text{H}_2/\text{CO}_2 = 3$; $SW = 1$ bar were used for the PBMR.

I.). This is also predicted by the PBMR model. The slightly lower accuracy of the PBMR model in these conditions can be ascribed to the fact that when the CO₂ and H₂ concentration approaches zero, the model becomes unstable (i.e., the denominator of the kinetic rate expressions depends on these nearly zero CO₂ and H₂ partial pressures).

Better performance is expected for SW ratios larger than 1, which could not be tested due to the limitation of the MFCs.

4.3.5. Stability test

The productivity of the PBMR in terms of DME flow rate in both retentate (F_{DME}^R) and permeate (F_{DME}^P) streams was recorded with time during the stability test (Fig. 9). The DME flow in the permeate stream allows to identify three regions:

1. In the first region, the F_{DME}^P increases up to a maximum since the CMSM is desorbing the water previously adsorbed during the catalyst

Fig. 9. DME flow in the retentate (blue symbols) and permeate (red symbols) stream as a function of the time on stream, monitored during the stability test carried out at $P^R = 40$ bar, $T = 200$ °C, GHSV of $400 \text{ NLkg}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$, $SW = 5$, $\Delta P = 0$ and a feed composition of $\text{H}_2/\text{CO}_2 = 3$.

reduction step (i.e., $\text{CuO}_{(s)} + \text{H}_2_{(g)} \rightarrow \text{Cu}_{(s)} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_{(g)}$). As water desorbs from the membrane pores, the active pore size increases, which corresponds to a higher DME permeance.

2. In the second region, the F_{DME}^P decreases, since the CMSM is stabilizing with the humidity content of the reaction zone. Indeed, the separation performance of carbon membranes are very sensitive to the humidity conditions. Different level of humidity corresponds to a different active pore size, which can significantly affect the extent of gas permeation and its mechanism [67–69].
3. In the third and last zone, the PBMR performance stabilize to the values reported in the previous section for this experimental conditions. Both F_{DME}^R and F_{DME}^P achieves a constant value, which leads to an overall DME yield of 14.3 %.

It should be noted that a full carbon balance was respected at all times, also during the dynamic (first and second) regions. When more DME is produced, less methanol is detected.

From this experiment, it is possible to conclude that the PBMR performance are stable in these conditions and that no deactivation phenomena are observed for neither the membrane nor the catalyst.

The PBMR performance reported in the previous sections correspond to their steady-state value (i.e., region 3). Indeed, after the reduction step, the membrane was first stabilized at the reaction temperature and under inert flow (N₂), to remove the extra water adsorbed. Thereafter, reaction was started and the performance were analysed after ca. 12 h.

5. Conclusions

This study demonstrates, at laboratory scale, that the incorporation of carbon molecular sieve membranes in conventional packed bed reactors allows for an improvement, in most of the cases, in the performance of the one-step CO₂ conversion to DME.

In order to demonstrate the PBMR technology, the activity of the CuO-ZnO-Al₂O₃/HZSM-5 bifunctional catalyst for the CO₂ hydrogenation to DME was first assessed in a PBR. The catalyst was found to be active and stable for this reaction. Furthermore, the kinetic model developed in previous studies describes well the reaction performance in the range of conditions of interest for this study (i.e., 10–40 bar and 200–260 °C).

Due to small modification in the membrane preparation procedure (i.e., dilution of the dipping solution), the CMSM used in this work showed

a much higher water permeance with respect to the membranes we studied in the previous works (i.e., ϕ_{H_2O} one order of magnitude larger) and a consequently lower vapor/gas selectivity, especially for the H₂O/CO₂, H₂O/CO and H₂O/MeOH pairs. Despite the permeance of this CMSM not matching with the target previously set, the PBMR was found to outperform the PBR in most of the experimental conditions. In particular, the CO₂ conversion was found to be 35%–40% higher than the PBR, for a SW= 1 and $\Delta P = 0$. Lower GHSV led to larger improvement, due to the system approaching its thermodynamic equilibrium (i.e., higher concentration of water). Nevertheless, the PBMR improves CO formation more than DME (i.e., Y_{DME} and Y_{CO} improve of 27% and 75% at a GHSV of 400 $NLkg_{cat}^{-1}h^{-1}$, respectively), due to the considerably large extent of both CO and methanol removal from the reaction zone. Better membrane performance and the recirculation of the permeated methanol in the sweep gas would prevent this problem.

Expectedly, the SW ratio was found to have a positive effect on the reaction performance, with the removal of water achieving ca. 80% at SW= 5. Also in this case, due to the removal of methanol and CO (ca. 70%), Y_{DME} and Y_{CO} increase of 66% and 122%, respectively, for a SW= 5. Temperatures higher than 200 °C were found to improve the rWGS reaction more than the DME synthesis, such that at 260 °C, the Y_{DME} of the PBMR is lower than for the PBR. This is because at higher temperature, given the fast reaction rates, product removal achieves ca. 98–99% for all species, due to the very large driving force. Thus, methanol cannot be converted to DME, while the removal of CO improves the rWGS. Finally, given the high permeability of this CMSM, higher ΔP were not beneficial on the reaction performance, due to the excessive loss of reactants (98–99% for a $\Delta P=3$ bar).

The stability of the PBMR was also tested for ca. 120 h, from which it was observed that the membrane needs some equilibration time to stabilize with the humidity condition of the reaction environment, after which the reaction performance are constant over time.

The reactor model developed in our previous studies was found to describe the performance of both the PBR and PBMR very accurately in the range of tested conditions. Nevertheless, in some cases, the model slightly underpredicts the Y_{CO} and Y_{MeOH} , while it estimates a slightly higher Y_{DME} than the experimental value. This difference can be ascribed to the CMSM permeation properties implemented in the model, which do not account for the interactions of the species in a multicomponent system.

In conclusion, although this study was not carried out with the optimal membrane as defined in previous studies, the improved performance of PBMR technology for the CO₂ hydrogenation to DME was demonstrated. Most importantly, the reactor models developed and extensively used in other studies, were hereby validated. This means that, with optimal membrane properties, even better performance are expected. Nevertheless, as also concluded in our previous study, the PBMR conditions, especially in terms of SW and ΔP , can be further optimized as a function a specific set of membrane properties, for example to address poor perm-selectivity/high permeability issues. This guarantees robust and effective operation of the PBMR.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

S. Poto: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft. **A. Pacheco Tanaka:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **M. Llosa Tenco:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **F. Neira d'Angelo:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **F. Gallucci:** Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Methodology.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jcou.2023.102513](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2023.102513).

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